

CRAFTSMANSHIP PRECEPTS FOR DESIGN PRACTICE

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ABSTRACT

The article proposes a reflection on the designer's position as a producer of objects and an agent that modifies the environment in which we live. We begin with an overview of the present state of the profession, in which the designer is most of the time bound to the framework of industrial production and has little autonomy in what concerns the product of his work. What we seek to understand is how the use of principles inherent to the way of life and work of craftsmen, as conceptualized by two North American thinkers, Charles Wright Mills and Richard Sennett, may contribute to recovering autonomy, thus endowing designers with a more critical and independent character.

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INTRODUCTION

The convergence between design and crafts-based productive activities has produced a great number of papers in the institutional sphere. In Brazilian entities such as the Serviço de Apoio às Micro e Pequenas Empresas - SEBRAE (PROGRAMA SEBRAE DE ARTESANATO, 2004; FREITAS, COSTA e MENEZES, 2009), Serviço Nacional de Aprendizagem Rural - SENAR (2012), Empresa de Assistência Técnica e Extensão Rural — EMATER (Miranda, 2009), Programa do Artesanato Brasileiro — PAB, among others, as well as in the academic sphere, where the number of works is high. For instance, in the annals of the Brazilian Congress of Research and Development (Congresso Brasileiro de Pesquisa e Desenvolvimento Design - P&D Design) (biennial national event) held in 2012, out of 700 presentations given as complete papers, round tables, and poster presentations, roughly 100 titles dealt with the relation between Design and Crafts.

A lot has been published about and invested in bringing design and crafts together, especially on occasions when the designer acts as a consultant, facilitating the creation, development, and improvement of crafted products, and, sometimes, of their respective productive processes. This is a practice that has been growing stronger in Brazil, making great works

and partnerships possible. But thinking the other way around, what do craftwork and, more precisely, the craftsman have to teach designers? What can designers learn from them?

Designers, just as everyone else, live a 'consuming life' where happenings flow and nothing is ever completely established (Bauman, 2001). However designers have more responsibility, for they are producers, as well as consumers, and therefore can develop new ideas to transform their environment. In present times we see an instrumentalization of the designer's profession; an alienation from the productive intention, subdued by economic interests. Design thus loses its autonomy, and its creative potential while instead having to come up with solutions in an ever more complex world (Mills, 2008).

In this article, based on works of two North American thinkers, Charles Wright Mills and Richard Sennett, we deal with how designers can take on a more active role by revisiting concepts extracted from craftsmanship.

THE DESIGNER AND TIME

We live in a time when everything moves so fast that it does not become established, a time when things are born already doomed to death, be it technical, cultural or symbolic. At first

sight one might think that in such a context, in which consumption is higher than ever before, the designer, the professional that shapes new objects (for consumption) has never been better. However, we must notice that, behind such consumerism and fast emergence of new products, there is a professional who has been gradually losing his autonomy — a process that starts with the Industrial Revolution (the Arts and Crafts Movement being a symbol of resistance).

Today design and, as a consequence, designers became a tool for the industry to sell more. The latter are professionals specialized in manipulating signs to increase consumption. When we look at things from this perspective, the designer has been fulfilling his role — but should that be his only function? These authors we here do not think so. They argue that we need a more critical way of thinking about what we produce, and that there is an ethical question involved in launching products into the world. Among the problems inherent to design, Bernhard Bürdek (2005) corroborates the question, mentioning that ‘design should promote and communicate services, but also – pursued energetically enough – help to prevent products that are senseless’ (Bürdek, 2005, p.16).

INTELLECTUAL CRAFTSMANSHIP AND THE CRAFTSMAN

Charles Wright Mills, an American sociologist of the twentieth century, was interested in craftsmen. He saw in their work a new way of thinking sociology, and tried to capture that concept for sociological research and development. Mills felt sociology should be applied in ways that resulted in something relevant for societal development, and created a concept called ‘intellectual craftsmanship’, in which he draws a parallel between the way of life and production of craftsmen, and the way a sociologist should develop his or her thought and research. To him, craftsmen have several applicable values, as if sociologists were also craftsmen, but craftsmen of thought, a kind of thought, as he would later define more clearly, that does not become separated from action — ‘making is thinking’ (Sennet, 2012).

In a conference for designers entitled ‘The man in the middle: the designer’, Mills gives his interpretation of the North American designer and the scenario in which that professional works, and then explains what characterizes craftsmanship, drawing a parallel with design. Mills (2008, p.173) starts by saying that the designer has become an important part of economy, in which ‘his art is a business’, and where a certain development brought ‘art, science and learning into subordinate relation with the dominant institutions of the capitalist economy’. Because the productive capacity is much higher than demand, marketing techniques were developed that, combined with goods that wear out quickly, aim at keeping consumption always in expansion. In the authors’ view, there are three types of obsolescence,

- (1) technological, as when something wears out or something better is produced;
- (2) artificial, as when something is deliberately

designed so that it *will* wear out; and (3) status obsolescence, as when fashions are created in such ways that consumption brings disgrace or prestige in accordance with last year’s or this year’s model, and alongside the old struggle for existence, there is added the panic for status (Mills, 2008, p.177).

All that began in the 1920s, when production sped up considerably and supply became higher than demand, which led to the development of strategies for consumption to go on. The trend has only gotten worse now that the economy seems to be endlessly expanding. Among the three types described above, the third is the one where the designer has the greatest relevance, for ‘his economic task is to sell’ (Mills, 2008, p.177); his autonomy and intellectual capacity of critical thinking are subdued to the motto ‘God is the Big Sell’ (Mills, 2008, p.177), and he joins the company of other professionals who specialize in sales (advertisers, public relations, market researchers), whose goal is ‘less to make better products than to make products sell better’ (Mills, 2008, p.177).

There is a huge intellectual waste in looking for projects to deceive the customer and give him the impression of buying a sensation, status, and not the product itself. Designers themselves fall prey to such manipulation, as the market looks out for stars to add value to products, so that, becoming a star, a designer becomes a prisoner of his own success, and even if he gets tired of his style the demand for it forces him to keep it, in order to keep his status. On the other hand the situation is cruel for the rest of the population of designers, for ‘One is a smash hit or one is among the failures who are not produced; one is a best seller or one is among the hacks and failures; one is either absolutely tops or one is just nothing at all’ (Mills, 2008, p.179). Then if the designer does not fit into this system in order to reach the ideal standards established by the market, the latter demotes him. Living thus becomes a form of resistance or accommodation.

To wrap up the production frame in which designers work, the author emphasizes the fact that producers (designers, advertisement creators, people who conceive new objects) say ‘we only give them what they want’ (Mills, 2008, p.179). That is a deception that traps not only customers, but also the people making consumption objects. Society’s need is totally shaped to this or that product, ‘consumers are trained to “want” that to which they are most continually exposed’ (Mills, 2008, p.179).

There is no relevant evolution in the vast majority of products justifying their being thrown away so easily. Thus all the commercial apparatus is mobilized to create a desire for a determinate product which is ‘newer’, and therefore ‘more beautiful’ than the previous. The shorter the life cycle of a product is, the better it is to keep that movement, which alienates and is in a sense cruel to people (most) who cannot keep up with the changes and get frustrated because of it. The designer plays a fundamental role in this context, manipulating signs, stirring people’s desire.

So, for the designer to break away from that cycle and look for a less alienating type of production, which contributes to the development of culture and the improvement of the space in which we live, Mills proposes that he rethinks the

way of modifying not only himself, but also the environment where he lives, because the designer ‘is a creator and a critic of the physical frame of private and public life’ (Mills, 2008, p.181). Craftsmanship is the way to do it; not only as an ideal, but also as a practice. Explaining what he understands as craftsmanship, the author lists five points.

The first and the second are related to freedom in work, for ‘in craftsmanship there is no ulterior motive for work other than the product being made and the process of its creation’ (Mills, 2008, p.181). Things are made for personal satisfaction, even if it lies in the satisfaction of another, the craftsman does not dissociate from the product of his work, he is always thinking about it, in its development, in the process and the final piece. The aesthetic experience that can be apprehended in the creation of those objects is transported to users, for ‘in an impersonal, scheduled, a machined world, they (crafted objects) represent the personal and the spontaneous. They are the opposite of the stereotyped and the banalized’ (Mills, 2008, p.181). The plan and the execution of work do not dissociate, and ‘the craftsman is master of the activity and of himself in the process’ (Mills, 2008, p.182). There is freedom in the execution of work, carried out according to personal preferences and experiences, and the craftsman is also free if he wants to change something during the process, which is conscious because the process is mastered as a whole, through conception, planning and execution: ‘Work is a rational sphere of independent action’ (Mills, 2008, p.182). The craftsman changes the way he works during the process of execution thinking of the meta-image he has in mind, so that he imagines all ways and mechanisms to reach the closest result to that image, and as the product materializes such process goes on, in the search of the best way to come to the desired result.

The third and fourth points deal with how work contributes to self-development, and how the relationship with work is contained in the craftsman’s relationship with life. As techniques improve, so does thought, and vice versa. When he carries out his work, the craftsman is going through meaningful experiences, and when work stops for a moment, he is not interrupting the experience, but catching his breath to keep going. Creative and productive experience is so ingrained in the craftsman’s life context that he does not disconnect himself from his activity as a craftsman when engaged in other activities. The same happens, or should happen, according to Mills, with designers.

In the fifth and last point the author emphasizes the importance of people who feed those ideas, for ‘Such an independent stratum of craftsmen cannot flourish unless there are publics who support individuals who may not turn out to be first-rate’ (Mills, 2008, p.182).

There is a restriction in the scenario we live, where the model makes decisions to be determined by the economic character, often limiting the designer’s responsibility and critical thinking. That question is discussed by Richard Sennett, another North American sociologist, posterior to Mills, in the beginning of his book *The Craftsman*. He quotes a sentence from his professor and supervisor Hannah Arendt to sum up that initial situation: ‘people who make things usually don’t

understand what they are doing’ (Sennett, 2008, p.1), and, he adds, take ‘the work as an end in itself’ (Sennett, 2008, p.6), thus raising the discussion of the relation between technique and thought in which one questions the responsibility that befalls (or not) people who develop and create new things. It would then be necessary to think of things before effectively building them, and predict the impacts they might have, both the benefits and harms. Sennett quotes the inventor of the atomic bomb, among others, to illustrate the idea that people seek development on its own, without critically thinking about the relevance of what they are doing, and leaving political and economic decisions to guide development. When that happens, those interests may not converge into ethical attitudes and may end up producing catastrophic results.

Designers have been suffering from apathy and passively wait for the industry to set the guidelines for configuring new objects. A wider critical view of the implications of what is being developed, so that by solving a problem we do not create a bigger one. Such as Sennett suggests, the philosopher Flusser (2008) formulates the question, stating that often, or even all the time, we remove obstacles by placing other obstacles in the way. That is, when we do not think about what we are doing, we simply allow more obstacles to get in our way. However, when we assume the attitude of craftsmen trying to master the totality of our acts we can develop relevant things.

Craftsmen’s knowledge was built through the sharing of skills among people, as well as by passing them down to the following generations. The formation of craftsmen happened through others’ knowledge, ‘personal genius had little meaning in this context’ (Sennett, 2008, p.22). Mills’ idea, presented in the beginning, might sound idealistic, but Sennett believes that open source software, such as Linux, is an excellent example of the application of elements typical of craftsmen; for information is totally shared and the search for improvement is constant.

A community of craftsmen (...) is focused on achieving quality, on doing good work, which is the craftsman’s primordial mark of identity. In the traditional world of the archaic potter or doctor, standards for good work were set by the community, as skills passed down from generation to generation (Sennett, 2008, p.25).

There is impersonality of work, and, on the other hand, no predominant intention driving the development, except getting to improve the program at each new version. In design there is the idea of *open design*, where creations are shared, not only by other designers, but also by people, potential customers who want to give their opinion about the subject. However, we do not see the same degree of sharing here as in the creation of open source software.

Sennett stresses the importance of repetition for learning, and how that was lost with the advent of new technologies. There is today a distance between head and hand, the opposite of the fundamental characteristic of all craftsmanship. CAD tools, which are extremely important for the modern world, Such proximity is reduced, for example, by CAD tools, but they also limit thought, once they do not allow one to ‘do it, (...) redo it, and (...) redo it again’ (Renzo Piano, quoted by

Sennett, 2008, p.40). The speed at which a mistake is corrected makes its comprehension impossible, thus preempting the concept of repetition, as explored by Walter Benjamin (1992) in his text 'One way Street'. As Benjamin writes, there is a very big difference between flying over a road and walking on it; that is, the view that one has when one must get close to the object by repetition is much richer, and the process of repetition allows that. Benjamin mentions the example of Chinese copiers: 'Only the copied text thus commands the soul of him who is occupied with it, whereas the mere reader never discovers the new aspects of his inner self that are opened by the text...' (Benjamin, 1979, p. 50). Another great limitation of CAD tools is the exactness of algorithms, which cannot allow for all conceivable possibilities; even if they get very good, we will be limited to an interface that responds to commands that are not our own.

THE DESIGNER AS A CRAFTSMAN

The concepts introduced by the authors might be seen as a union of theory and practice, head and hand. By becoming also the producer of his creations the designer cannot only better develop his own ideas, but also apprehend the process. And once he is shaping something he imagined, to which he can give his enthusiasm and dedication, the designer works harder, and gains relevant experience of his trade. There is today a distance between the people who think the world and the people who make and build this world — a distance between art and technique. The designer might play a fundamental role in this situation, as a professional who can work in that interface, bringing both elements closer. Art and technique are sometimes seen as opposites, but, when brought together, they can contribute to improve our experience of the world, insofar as one thinks about objects as possibilities, as ways to interact with others, and to stimulate increased understanding and cooperation among people.

Both Mills and Sennett emphasize the importance of strengthening that relation to create a greater connection with work. The pragmatist current of thought to which Sennett belongs emphasizes that 'to work well people need freedom from means-ends relationships' (Sennett, 2008, p.288), and in order to get that we must understand 'the value of experience understood as a craft' (Sennett, 2008, p.288), where the trade of producing material things gives one a better understanding of others; once 'the craft of making things provides insight into the techniques of experience that can shape our dealings with others' (Sennett, 2008, p.289).

There are great challenges to be overcome, once the current model asserts itself, and the social value given to the craftsman (and the designer) is low. There is a conflict between nature and culture; the natural productive action of craftsmen opposes the current cultural apparatus. An improvement in that apparatus is needed so that no conflict between them arises. For the designer to work according to crafts precepts, beyond his will, a greater interest is needed, a support, as Mills claims.

Today we can be anywhere through the Internet, and the circulation of new ideas is easier. With tools like crowd funding those ideas become viable without the support of any big companies. In such initiatives there are crafts precepts, such as reciprocal cooperation, exchange of information, collective creation, organization in nets and communities; all of those listed by Sennett (2008). The main objective is not economic. As we can see in Saramago's *The Cave*, for a craftsman his trade is not solely about making a living; even if he wants to do something else, he cannot, he cannot work if not with that; what he experiences there is so pleasant and motivating that he cannot think of anything else. There is pride in what he is doing, in the work of his hands (and head). That is what designers (and all other producers) are able to feel when they experience those concepts.

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